

**PRIMARY CLASS AND HIGH CLASS MATHEMATICS FROM SCIENCE
APPROPRIATION DIFFICULT HAS BEEN VISUAL TEACHING OF
ISSUES METHODOLOGY (FRACTIONS EXAMPLE)**

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Annotation: In this article Mathematics from science initial class and high class student and future of teachers appropriations difficult has been of issues lighting and this issues of what consists of that determine, and appropriation difficult has been of issues in teaching computer technologies and computer from the games useful methods about data and of fractions private cases about data showing passed.

Key words: Fractions, Simple Fractions, correct fractions, incorrect fractions, decimals fractions, mixed numbers, math dictation.

As we all know, the science of mathematics itself is considered difficult to study and learn in comparison to other sciences. However, a more in-depth study of some topics in mathematics can increase interest in mathematics.

As an initial understanding of mathematics, it is appropriate to take the subject of fractions.

If we take into account one more thing, it is appropriate to use computer technology and computer games in the process of studying difficult-to-master problems in mathematics, and at the same time, the use of animated presentations in explaining the topic with the help of a computer. rni will also be of great importance. When creating an animated presentation, using eye-catching animations with moving shapes as much as possible can be considered as an effective method.

Focusing on the topic of fractions, it is good to explain the differences between simple fractions, decimals, correct fractions, incorrect fractions and mixed numbers using an animated animation.. If an example is given in the animation to distinguish the difference of fractions through objects used in everyday life, the pupil and student will remain deep in the memory of the youth, and there will be a chance to increase the mastery rate.

I think it is appropriate to use STEM technology to students and young students in order to explain the concept of fractions.

We can show as an example the act of being in the primary grade mathematics course when the topic of fractions is being explained to students and young students.

Only in the course of elementary mathematics, if a large number is divided by a small number without a remainder, and if there is a remainder, the remaining part of the number is marked as a remainder. Now we can convert a small number to a large number. it is enough to separate this situation with a simple caste line. When we divide a large number by a small number, if there is a remainder, the quotient is written as a whole number in the form of a divisible denominator and a remainder.

For example

Given of forms known part to paint through in months given topic about to think doilaerini expand and the subject explain part our facilitation can _ This is in STEMP technology given forms to make done through _ to increase can _ in STEMP technology shown of students own hand with maker things remembering to stay technology strong we also use the fact that can _

This is the case according to student in youth fraction about thoughts forming from being after of fractions private cases in line thought conduct to the part let's go will be In this basically right fractions, incorrect fractions, decimals fractions and mixed muscles about information by entering get to the goal according to will be

That's right and wrong the deaf about information in giving the most first of all right and wrong fractions about information by entering get to the goal according to will be 5th grade of mathematics in the chair right and wrong fractions about common data giving passed.

That's right given as a fraction of the fraction sutari from the denominator small if i.e small thigh big to the psalm to be to the situation it is said. For example $:\frac{2}{5}, \frac{3}{7}, \frac{5}{9}$

Wrong given as deaf of the fraction sutari from the denominator big if i.e Big thigh indivisible small to the psalm to be to the situation it is said. For example $:\frac{7}{5}, \frac{9}{7}, \frac{3}{2}$

We are a fraction numbers in chapter simple of fractions before shares we learn. Mathematics our teacher to a friend square drew and 4 pieces it happened. One piece _ colorful in the pen paint drew _ Teacher of the square how more _ paint. So, teacher 4 equals the square into pieces being and him one piece colorful pencil with paint. It is 4 of the square one that it was means _ A natural number n it can be said that it is the result of being gu. On the contrary $k:n = \frac{k}{n}$ or $\frac{k}{n} = k:n$ can be written in the form.

Example : $4:7 = \frac{4}{7}, 10:13 = \frac{10}{13}, \frac{3}{8} = 3:8, \frac{30}{17} = 30:17$

Har what natural number denominator is 1 _ see as a fraction can _

$$k = k:1 = \frac{k}{1}$$

Fraction line I to be practice means _

Example : $16 = \frac{16}{1}, 24 = \frac{24}{1}$

$\frac{k}{n}$ in writing k and n natural numbers, the following points can be made: 1) $k < n$, 2) $k > n$, 3) $k = n$ in these points we make fractions as follows.

If $k < n$ if there is a correct fraction, $k > n, k = n$ if there is an incorrect fraction.

Photo from the denominator small was _ fraction right fraction is called That's right fraction always from 1 small will be

Photo from the denominator big or to the denominator equal to fraction wrong _ fraction is called Incorrect _ fractions from 1 big or 1 ha equal to will be

Example :

$\frac{4}{7}; \frac{15}{18}; \frac{19}{28}; \frac{5}{9}; \frac{16}{27}; \frac{50}{100}; \frac{65}{75}$ - proper fractions ;

$\frac{11}{10}; \frac{20}{17}; \frac{8}{8}; \frac{26}{13}; \frac{30}{30}; \frac{18}{9}$ - wrong fractions.

Of two natural numbers division _ that's it of thighs ratio is called

Example : 5 apples to 2 children equal to be lib you want to give Har one to the child from how many touch _

1st child $2 + \frac{1}{2} = 2\frac{1}{2}$

2nd child $2 + \frac{1}{2} = 2\frac{1}{2}$

So, from 2 and a half apple touches _ $2\frac{1}{2}$ the number is a mixed number.

Incorrect _ from the fraction is a mixed number product to do can _

For example : $\frac{24}{5} = 4\frac{4}{5}, \frac{37}{10} = 3\frac{7}{10}, \frac{17}{5} = 3\frac{2}{5}, \frac{20}{11} = 1\frac{9}{11}$

A mix thigh wrong _ fraction in the form of to write can _

For example : $4\frac{4}{5} = \frac{24}{5}, 3\frac{5}{7} = \frac{26}{7}, 5\frac{3}{4} = \frac{23}{4}$.

Mathematician of dictations advantages about speaking if i pass

Mathematician dictation knowledge control of doing famous shape is a school mathematics teachers by active is used. This of the event essence from that is that the teacher question gives (oral or written), students while short the answers their writing need _ Before school age to the child dictation duties visual respectively perform offer to be done can :

- cubes again in order put _
- shown buttons the number add / delete ;

- present done objects groups compare ;
- objects known one way grouping.

Mathematician dictations in classification different of criteria use can _ Most of the time mathematician dictations solution who does to tasks according to to groups divided into :

- mathematician terminology take over
- mental to count to teach
- makes sense questions.

Blending for different different types Mathematician dictations recommendation not, although it is acceptable that is considered Task in making main thing him known one of the child (or children in kindergarten mathematics about speaking if) knowledge level is adaptation.

Mathematician dictation of the child attention sum up ability perfect level teaches. Task successful perform for baby significant the will manifestation to do need :

- the assignment attention with listen _
- what to do need identify to give Demand without doing (preferably !) enough fast _
- your answer write (task do).

Perfect mathematician speech development mathematician of dictations advantages also related to to be need :

- the boy is a mathematician expressions right study listens ;
- thematic the dictionary enriches ;
- arithmetic deeds and geometric of figures names strengthens _

Too bad except not working and this kind of to the activity interest not to lose for of your ward situation follow up. Mathematician of dictation average duration is 7 minutes. Of course, if your in your family all tasks from doing happy has been young mathematician growing up if so, you recommendation done from time more time your work can _ But force no ! This important, friends.

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